

FACTOR IMPACT ON CORPORATE FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE: EVIDENCE FROM JORDAN

MOHAMMAD TAYSEER ALSHABOUL

UCSI Graduate Business School, UCSI University, Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia.

AI-FEN LIM

UCSI Graduate Business School, UCSI University, Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia.

Abstract

*This study investigates the influence of corporate governance mechanisms on corporate financial performance in Jordanian listed corporations. It also explores the impact of Risk committee and corporate social responsibilities on corporate financial performance. Corporate financial performance is measured using return on assets (ROA) and Tobin's Q. This study covers all the industrial and service corporations listed on Amman Stock Exchange (ASE) from 2017 to 2022 (N = 426). **Finding:** The result indicates the board of director size is significantly linked with corporate financial performance as measured by Tobin Q. On the other hand, there is no relationship between the board of director size and return on assets. Moreover, there is not a significant relationship between board Independence and return on assets. In addition, there is a negative impact of board Independence on Tobin Q. Regarding the board of director meeting the result indicates there is a positive impact of board meetings on corporate financial performance as measured by ROA and Tobin Q. On the other hand, the finding indicates that CEO duality impact return on assets but doesn't impact Tobin Q. Furthermore, the finding mentioned the audit committee size impact corporate financial performance as measured by return on assets and Tobin Q. The finding of this study indicates that there is no association among audit committee meeting and return on assets. On the other contrary, the finding indicates there is a relation between audit committee meetings and Tobin Q. Additionally, there is a significant relation between corporate social responsibility (community and environment) and corporate financial performance as measured by return on assets and Tobin Q. Finally, the existence of risk committee will impact corporate financial performance as measured by return on assets and Tobin Q. This study concludes that good corporate governance mechanisms play a key role in improving the performance of corporations. The current study presents practical evidence to the policymakers, academicians, and all related parties in emerging markets, specifically in Jordan.*

Keywords: Corporate Governance, Board of Directors, Audit Committee, Risk Committee, Community and Environment Committee, Corporate Financial Performance.

INTRODUCTION

The concept of corporate governance (CG) has garnered significant global attention due to its potential as a valuable mechanism for addressing and mitigating corporate crises. Additionally, it serves as a foundational element for corporations to augment their value by establishing a competitive edge, fostering improved performance, and ultimately contributing to overall economic advancement within a nation. Both applications have the potential to reduce or mitigate any corporate crises, and both facets may play a role in the fact that CG is such a prevalent topic of conversation. According to researchers, having an efficient CG system boosts corporate financial performance and enhances profits (Al Farooque et al., 2020). The Ministry of Industry and Trade in Jordan has implemented governance measures to promote consistent economic growth. This involves enacting and enhancing

legislation, policies, and programmes to enhance the investment climate in Jordan. The ultimate goal is to position Jordan as a highly appealing economy in the Middle East, as stated in the Jordanian CG Code of 2017. The CG code in Jordan is particularly applicable to public shareholding corporations, private shareholding corporations, non-profit private shareholding corporations, limited liability corporations, and non-profit limited liability corporations. The law seeks to provide directives to the aforementioned categories of organisations to enhance their sustainability and performance, augment their worth, and facilitate their access to affordable financial resources. The law seeks to provide directives to the aforementioned categories of organisations to enhance their sustainability and performance, augment their worth, and facilitate their access to low-cost financial.

According to the ASE (2019), Jordanian industrial and service corporations perform poorly, decreasing shareholder and investor trust in publicly listed corporations. The COVID-19 pandemic has posed a severe economic and social shock to all countries, including Jordan. With the slowing growth that Jordan had witnessed before the pandemic, this shock is expected to be more severe. This negative impact is expected to affect several sectors, especially trade, tourism, services, and industrial sectors (Alkayed, H., & Omar, B. F. 2023 & World Bank Group, 2020). Moreover, (Nawaiseh 2015) mentioned that the performance level of Jordanian corporations in the industrial and service sectors is considerably lower than that of financial corporations, thus raising serious concerns amongst Jordanian regulators and decision-makers. They indicate that this low performance is due to corporate misunderstandings and a lack of guidance from the ASE to them about CG code (Alkurdi et al., 2021).

For the past few years, publicly traded corporations in Jordan have been suffering from poor performance (Alkurdi et al., 2021). Negative results have been occurring for corporations in Jordan, which has resulted in a decline in terms of the quality of the financial reporting produced as well as a decline in repute. Consequently, the trust and faith of investors and shareholders in those corporations have been undermined (Alharasis et al., 2023).

Concerns on the part of shareholders have been raised because of these difficulties regarding the critical requirement for an improvement in CG to achieve performance goals (Karim et al., 2023). As was indicated earlier, the poor performance of Jordanian registered corporations in ASE is linked to deficiencies in the CG processes of these corporations (Makhlouf et al., 2017). In 2017, the European Bank for Reconstruction and Development tried to investigate the current state of CG in Jordan.

According to what they discovered, there is a lack of maturity among the corporations operating in Jordan in terms of CG. In 2022, (Nsour, and Al-Rjoub, 2022) discovered that Jordanian corporations did not progress in CG reform. In instances of inadequate governance, CEOs or Top Management Teams possess the ability to direct their organisation to make charitable contributions that conform to their inclinations but do not provide advantages for shareholders. Consequently, organisations with robust CG are likely to get a more favourable response from shareholders (Azuma, et al., 2023).

Furthermore, it is noteworthy that 84% of investors in Jordan exhibit a preference for investing in firms that adhere to robust CG practices, as delineated in the Jordanian CG Code of 2017. Several studies conducted in Jordan, including (Gerged et al., 2023 and Almarayeh, 2023), have shown that there is a link among CG and financial performance of a corporation.

These studies revealed their findings based on the Jordanian Corporate Governance Code, which was established in 2009. Furthermore, most of the study has been done on Jordan based on data before 2017, based on compliance and guidance strategy before improving the CG code by Jordan Securities Commission (JSC) and make it compulsory for all listed corporation in ASE. To address this gap, this research will focus on the period from 2017-2023.

Hypothesis Development

Agency Theory

Agency theory serves as the theoretical foundation for the vast majority of accounting studies (Jensen & Meckling, 1976). The hypothesis aims to explain the connection between shareholders and managers. When shareholders hire managers to undertake responsibilities on their behalf, an agency relationship is formed. Due to the separation of ownership and management in corporate organisations, however, the interaction between inside managers and outside stockholders is fraught with competing interests. For example, managers may not always behave in the best interests of shareholders. When possibilities occur, they could pursue their own private incentives at the expense of shareholders (Yunos, 2011). Elements of CG, such as the BODs and the AC, assist in minimising agency conflicts inside the corporation (Yunos, 2011). Such disagreements are kept to a minimum by corporations that have strong governance, especially when all of the interests of the stockholders are taken into consideration. According to (Habbash 2010), one of the major difficulties addressed by the agency theory is that corporate Supervisors attempt to maximise their own personal interest by providing incorrect financial information to the harm of creditors or shareholders. Consequently, this issue highlights the necessity to ensure that corporate managers can be counted on to serve the organization's interests and not simply their own (Habbash, 2010). Efficient CG shall be seen as a method to eliminate agency struggle, especially when the conflict concerns the interests of all shareholders. This is especially true when the disagreement encompasses the interests of both parties. This is especially the case when the dispute is about the potential value of the corporation. In a similar spirit, (Hashim and Abdul Rahman, 2010) arrived at the opinion that CG serves as a regulation instrument to defend against selfish managerial behaviour. They came to this result after conducting research in the same vein. In the meantime, (Shukeri and Islam, 2012) highlighted research that demonstrated how applying agency theory to CG processes improved the financial performance of corporations.

Resource Dependence Theory

The central principle of the RDT posits that the competitive strategies used by corporations in the marketplace are contingent upon the resources at their disposal. The pertinence of this concept to the ongoing inquiry is in the potential of effective CG to provide resources that possess economic worth. To enhance specificity, while establishing connections with other entities, the BODs may function as a valuable resource for knowledge and management expertise. In contrast, the use of sample phrases may serve as an illustrative instance, wherein the board emerges as a particularly discernible asset for the corporation.

Many researchers such as (Pucheta-Martínez, & Gallego-Álvarez, 2020), argued that directors play a crucial role as the main providers of information and gatekeepers to other corporations and financial markets. Social capital and human capital are the two main classifications of resources that constitute BODs. The board is comprised of the following resources. The concept of human capital pertains to the cognitive capacities of directors, including factors like education, quality of education, experience, and related attributes. On the other hand, social capital pertains to the directors' affiliations with external businesses and the extent to which these affiliations provide valuable resources for the businesses. Furthermore, the use of resource dependence theory was utilized to examine resources on both large and small boards. According to (Pfeffer, 1972), it has been observed that boards play a crucial role in providing resources to businesses. Consequently, bigger boards tend to need a greater number of external members, which in turn influences the decision-making and activities of these corporations. The presence of several individuals who are not part of the board brings about a range of personal and social resources, so enhancing their ability to make valuable contributions to the

board's endeavors. A multitude of scholarly investigations have been conducted to explore the connection between board resource supply and corporate financial performance (Dalton and Kesner, 1987). As indicated by (Psaros, 2009), CG is contingent upon the provision of resources. Various authors provide a range of resources to organizations to establish their distinctiveness via the ownership structure. The use of human and social capital has the potential to enhance a corporation's competitive advantage. According to previous research conducted by (Hillman et al., 2000), the boarding tunnel plays a crucial role in making strategic decisions, while the board capital has a significant effect on the financial performance of corporations.

Board Size and Corporate Financial Performance

The JCGC 2009, which applies to corporations with shares listed on the ASE, suggests there should be between five and thirteen people on the board (JSC, 2017). The number of directors serving on the board is an important factor in establishing effective CG mechanisms. The influence of the number of directors on a corporation may frequently be seen in the degree to which boards participate in corporate activities and concerns (Alagha, 2016). The number of directors occupying the seats on the corporation's BODs is represented by the size of the BODs. The BODs are widely regarded as the heart of CG, and it is the primary way by which shareholders can exert indirect control on top management. (Fauzi and Locke 2012) argued that increased board size (BISZ) is positively connected with more corporate monitoring. (Abdou et al., 2021) found that corporations with larger boards of directors have a lower incidence of earning management. On the other hand, (Jamaludin, et al., 2015) discovered that smaller boards had a greater propensity to be unsuccessful in identifying income management. In addition, a few studies (Talbi et al., 2015) discovered an essential association between BISZ and corporate financial performance. In Jordan, (Jaafar and El-Shawa, 2009) have analyzed the influence of BISZ on corporate performance. They discovered that the connection between BISZ and corporate financial performance is significant and positive. Unlike that, (Alabdullah et al., 2014) found it to be negative. (Abed et al., 2012) analyzed the relationship between BISZ and caring management and found that the number of BODs has a significant negative relation with corporate financial performance. According to agency theory, the corporate director monitors the performance and activities of the managers as a representation of the corporate numerous owners and stakeholders. A larger BODs has more directors working for the stakeholders' best interests. According to agency theory, larger BODs improve corporate financial performance by enhancing the monitoring role (Badu & Appiah, 2017).

Hypothesis 1_a: There is association among board of directors' size and corporate financial performance as measured by return on assets (ROA).

Hypothesis 1_b: There is association among board of directors' size and corporate financial performance as measured by Tobin Q.

Board Independence and Corporate Financial Performance

Members of the board who are not tied to the corporate, higher executive management, corporate affiliations, or external auditors through financial interests other than held shares are referred to as independent board members (ASE, 2017). The concept of independence in CG refers to the ability of board members to make decisions and carry out their responsibilities without being influenced or reliant on the CEO or management. This aspect of independence is influenced by the membership of the board, as discussed by (Swamy 2011). External board members, sometimes referred to as outside directors, lack significant affiliations with the corporation and do not actively participate in the corporation's day-to-day activities. Nevertheless, the individuals in question are actively engaged in the decision-making processes of the corporation and exhibit a higher degree of autonomy in executing their responsibilities, so contributing to the overall operational efficacy of the corporation.

Moreover, the experiences of individuals will contribute to the generation of novel ideas and alternative viewpoints about the financial performance of the corporation (Swamy, 2011). Board independence (BIND) is a new metric for assessing BODs qualities that has piqued the interest of academics and practitioners alike. Previous studies on the subject have shown a variety of results. Few research has found a connection between external directors' presence and corporate financial performance (Makhlouf et al., 2017; Abu-Risheh and Al-Sa'eed, 2012). On the other hand, (Vu & Nguyen 2017) found no significant link. While (Iskandar et al., 2011) have demonstrated that external directors are better competent to regulate and monitor management in specific settings such as financial performance. According to the agency theory, there is a favorable connection between BIND and corporate financial performance. Numerous research has found that the makeup of the BODs has a favorable impact on corporate financial performance, whether in developed or developing countries. On the other side, studies undertaken in emerging nations have found positive associations between BIND and corporate financial performance (Chechet et al, 2013). Other research, such as (Alix Valenti et al., 2011), found unfavorable associations between BIND and the financial performance of a corporation.

H2_a: There is association among board of directors' independence and corporate financial performance as measured by return on assets (ROA).

H2_b: There is association among board of directors' independence and corporate financial performance as measured by Tobin Q.

Board Meeting and Corporate Financial Performance

A Jordanian corporation's BODs must be met by an official letter from the chairman or a written request by 25% of board members. Meetings of the BODs can be held at any time. These are the two approaches that are utilised in the process of calling meetings to be held. Furthermore, it is essential that voting on the decision made by the BODs is conducted only by in-person participation. Any kind of participating by proxy, letter, or any other kind of indirect participation method is strictly prohibited. After that, the decisions that were reached by the BODs need to be ratified and sanctioned by an overwhelming majority of the board who attended the meetings. More importantly, the BODs are mandated to hold a minimum of one meeting every two months, with the stipulation that the total number of board meetings held in a single financial year should be larger than four. This is one of the most important requirements for the BODs. During these sessions, the appointment of the board secretary will be delegated to the BODs as their responsibility. The board secretary is going to be the one in charge of recording the minutes and decisions of the meetings, as well as the members who attended the meeting and the input, in a particular report with sequential numbers (JSC, 2017). Meetings of the BODs are essential because they are held on behalf of the corporate by the BODs, and there is a procedure that involves the BODs taking collective action, which includes voting on resolutions pertaining to the meetings. When the BODs get together more frequently, they have more opportunities to deliberate over a variety of options, which speeds up the process of arriving at a conclusion (Khan et al., 2011). In addition, the efficacy of the board is dependent on the number of times it convenes, as this can aid an enhancement in the performance of the corporation. This is because more meetings provide the board with more opportunities to review and monitor the performance of management. In addition, BODs frequently step up the number of times they get together to hasten the discovery of answers to issues relating to a downturn in the performance of the corporation (Hsu & Petchsakulwong, 2010). The notion posits that board meetings have the potential to provide valuable insights on the extent of engagement. According to (Issarawornrawanich, 2015), it may be inferred that a higher frequency of board meetings may result in enhanced corporate financial performance. Considering this perspective, the regularity of board

meetings aligns with the principles of agency theory, which highlight the enhanced powers of corporate BODs in terms of providing guidance and oversight (Al-Manaseer et al., 2012).

H3_a: There is link between board of directors' meeting and corporate financial performance as measured by return on assets (ROA).

H3_b: There is link between board of directors' meeting and corporate financial performance as measured by Tobin Q.

CEO Duality and Corporate Financial Performance

Considering that the Chief Executive Officer (CEO) is an integral part of the CG process, there is no doubt that both the job of the board chairperson and the position of the CEO are essential. Duality occurs when the chief executive officer of a corporation also serves as the chairman of the board (Palanissamy, 2015). According to the JCGC (2009), the regulations prohibit the consolidation of the position of BODs chairman with any executive position inside the corporation (JSC, 2017). According to the agency theory, the roles of chief executive officer and chairman of the BODs should not be mixed because it is the board's duty to oversee and exercise authority over the CEO (Yunos, 2011). In Jordan, the Chairman of the board and the CEO had distinct roles, in keeping with the agency theory and the JCGC. Therefore, in order to avoid any conflicts of interest and to maintain managerial oversight, the roles should be split between two people. Independent directors should be given priority when the board is selecting a chairperson (JSC, 2017). Hence, the ability of the BODs to evaluate performance may be hindered if the person who runs the organization is also the person who chairs board meetings and oversees internal information that is supplied to the BODs (Baliga, et al., 1996). As mentioned by (Fauver et al., 2017), the presence of a distinct separation between the CEO and chairman positions contributes to the improved efficacy of the BODs. This is mostly due to the executive directors having a greater understanding of business matters in comparison to the independent members. In their study, (Withers and Fitza, 2017) presented two contrasting viewpoints to elucidate the rationale for the division and consolidation of responsibilities between the CEO and chairman positions. These views revolve on the notions of efficient oversight and robust leadership structure. The authors further recognized that the independent structure is favored by financial groups and practitioners. On the contrary, (Al Manaseer et al., 2012) and According to the findings of (Alabdullah et al., 2014), there is a negative connection among the separation of chairman and CEO duties and performance. (Abed et al., 2012) conducted research in Jordan to investigate how having a dual role as CEO affects the financial performance of a corporation. They concluded that there is a correlation, albeit weak.

H4_a: There is link between CEO duality and corporate financial performance as measured by return on assets (ROA).

H4_b: There is link between CEO duality and corporate financial performance as measured by Tobin Q ratio.

Audit Committee Size and Corporate Financial Performance

The size of the auditing board is determined by the number of individuals who serve on the audit committee of the organization (Obiyo & Lenee, 2011). According to the agency theory viewpoint, the conflict between management and shareholders often leads to a situation where top management prioritizes their own interests, particularly when the management exhibits opportunistic behavior (Ning et al., 2017). Furthermore, according to (Abdullah et al., 2014), using the resource dependency theory viewpoint suggests that enlarging the committee size could reduce the occurrence of unethical behavior and enhance the financial performance of corporations.

According to JCGC (2009), the regulations stipulate that a corporation must establish an audit committee consisting of at least three people (JSC, 2017). To look on the bright side, the size of the audit committee is highly significant for the effectiveness of corporation (Hamdan et al., 2013). As mentioned by the findings of (Al- Matari, et al., 2012), the performance of the corporation will suffer if there are an excessive number of members serving on the committee.

According to the agency theory, the interaction between top managers and shareholders is fraught with competing interests. These competing interests are the result of the separation of ownership and administration, as well as the different goals of top managers and investors. For instance, managers may make opportunistic use of the accounting discretion available to them to attain some of their own private motivations. audit committee is one technique to incentivize shareholders to employ procedures to prevent unpleasant managing activities. This can be accomplished by preventing undesirable managerial activities. As a direct result of this, CG was developed to reduce the likelihood of conflicts arising among managers and shareholders, in addition to bringing down the costs of agency representation for everyone involved (Fama & Jensen, 1983; Jensen & Meckling, 1976).

H5_a: There is relation among audit committee size and corporate financial performance as measured by return on assets (ROA).

H5_b: There is link among audit committee size and corporate financial performance as measured by Tobin Q.

Audit Committee Meetings and Corporate Financial Performance

The objective of the meeting is to engage in a comprehensive discussion and devise effective solutions to address the challenges currently confronting the organization. Hence, a higher frequency of meetings facilitates a greater resolution of difficulties. According to the resource dependency theory, the exchange of ideas and viewpoints plays a crucial role in addressing, evaluating meeting agendas, and resolving met difficulties (Hahn & Lasfer, 2016). From an agency theory standpoint, it may be argued that increasing the frequency of audit committee meetings serves to alleviate the agency issue. However, it is worth noting that such an increase in meeting frequency may also be indicative of subpar corporate financial performance. According to the regulations outlined in the JCGC (2009), it is mandatory for the audit committee to convene on a frequency exceeding four occasions during a year. Furthermore, it is essential that accurate and suitable minutes be recorded during these sessions, as stipulated by the (JSC 2017).

In general, a comprehensive analysis of the literature that is currently available indicated that there is no definitive link between the AC meetings and the performance of the corporation. There have only been a handful of studies that have looked at this connection and determined that there is a positive link between the AC meeting and corporate financial performance. Examples include (Chechet et al. 2013; Saibaba and Ansari 2011). On the other hand, (Hsu and Petchsakulwong, 2010) discovered that there is a negative relation between the AC meeting and corporate financial performance. On the other hand, (Ghabayen, 2012) found that there is no correlation between the attendance of audit committee meetings and the financial performance of the corporation.

H6_a: There is association among audit committee meeting and corporate financial performance as measured by return on assets (ROA).

H6_b: There is association among audit committee meeting and corporate financial performance as measured by Tobin Q.

Corporate Social Responsibility Committee and Corporate Financial Performance

The history of the idea of Corporate Social Responsibility, sometimes known as CSR, is lengthy and multifaceted. (Carroll, 1999) examined the history of CSR from the 1950s until the 1990s and explained the development of CSR as both a conceptual and definitional construct. His study covered the period from the 1950s until the 1990s.

CSR, or "Corporate Social Responsibility," was first coined by (Bowen, 1953), who is also known as the "Father of CSR." (Bowen 1953) described CSR as the obligation of corporation owners to be responsible for the repercussions of their actions in terms of the values that they provide to society. According to JCGC (2009), the CSR program among the publicly listed Jordanian corporation is composed of two dimensions, community and environmental. Thus, this study measured the community and environmental dimensions of CSR.

The term "community development" refers to the initiative that is made by a community in partnership with a corporation with the goal of empowering the community and providing for its essential requirements (Al-Smadi & Almsafir, 2016). The skills are centered on making use of the resources that are available in the immediate area and accumulating political influence by forming social groupings to accomplish a shared objective.

The people responsible for developing the community and every member of the community need to agree on how to make the most of the contributions of every member of society to the development of the community (Amran, et al., 2013). According to the description of what community development comprises that was given earlier, there are various ways in which CSR can influence community development (Roja & Sherina, 2015). As a result, engaging in socially responsible activities geared toward the improvement of the local community increases the loyalty of customers towards corporations.

However, this connection has not been fully established, and the mechanism between CSR and corporate financial performance is still not well understood by the previous studies (Alkhalaleh, 2016). Researchers have frequently argued that there is a positive relationship between CSR and corporate financial performance (Alkhalaleh, 2016). According to (Kitzmueller and Shimshack 2012), the reason why CSR is so important is that it ensures the corporation will have a positive image and reputation, and there is competition between corporations to apply the CSR actions.

This competition can be seen as corporate creating organisations to interest local communities, which can then lead to an enhancement of the corporate reputation and trust from the perspectives of people (Khasawneh & Al-Zawahreh 2015). There is a beneficial association between the community and environment and corporate performance, according to research conducted by (Flammer 2013). Furthermore, (Sahasranamam et al., 2020) suggest discovering the impact of CSR on corporate financial performance across other emerging and frontier markets in Africa and Asia.

H7_a: There is association among corporate social responsibility (community and environment) and corporate financial performance as measured by return on assets (ROA).

H7_b: There is association among corporate social responsibility (community and environment) and corporate financial performance as measured by Tobin Q.

Risk Committee and Corporate Financial Performance

As stated in the Jordanian Corporate Governance Code (2009), the BODs have the authority to form additional committees as required, taking into consideration the specific characteristics of the corporation's operations. The "other committees the BODs may establish such as CG committee, risk committee, human resources committee, executive committee, product development committee".

In today world, the risk committee has emerged as one of the most important players in current corporations' eras. This subcommittee is a part of the BODs, so it is anticipated to offer enough aid to the board and aid the corporation overseeing the managerial operation, both of which are intended to improve the performance of corporate and reduce the likelihood that earnings will be manipulated (Nava et al., 2009). According to the findings of a research project that was carried out by (Elamer, and Benyazid 2018) the Risk Committee plays an important part in lowering operational risks and improving financial performance.

The implementation of an effective risk should lead to a rise in the financial performance of the corporation (Malik, 2017). A risk committee is made up of methods and processes that are used by corporations to monitor risks and seize opportunities in a manner that is consistent with their essential goals. It is helpful to the senior managerial personnel since it ensures that the administration is accurately recognizing and assessing risks using standardized procedures.

(Brown, et al., 2009) mention that effective risk committee will result in ensuring fewer surprises, helping the executives and misuse of chances, improving data handling and correspondence, expanding corporate notoriety, improving the corporate stature responsibility, and improving financial performance. Several studies have highlighted the risk committee as a significant factor influencing the success of corporate financial performance.

The characteristics of the risk committee are likely to have a significant influence on the financial performance of a corporation (Aldhamari et al., 2020; Jia, et al., 2020). As a more recent development, BODs must implement a systematic risk management framework within corporations to supplement their supervisory responsibilities (De Zwaan et al., 2011).

The majority of the research that was looked at in the literature about the deployment of the risk committee and how well corporate perform suggests that effective utilization of risk committee will result in enhancing corporate financial performance (Schilling et al., 2012 and Kommunuri et al., 2016).

H8_a: There is association among risk committee and corporate financial performance as measured by return on assets (ROA).

H8_b: There is association among risk committee and corporate financial performance as measured by Tobin Q.

DATA AND METHODOLOGY

Panel data analysis is a regression technique that effectively combines time-series and cross-sectional data, making it a suitable approach for the present problem (Torres-Reyna, 2007). A researcher can incorporate in their study characteristics that cannot be quantified or observed, such as variances in corporation procedures across corporations or differences in culture across countries. This is made possible through panel data.

A researcher is also possible to analyse characteristics that vary over the course of time but remain consistent throughout corporations (Torres-Reyna, 2007). The data in this research is analysed using the SPSS version 23 statistical programme. The industrial, service, and financial sectors are the three categories into which these corporations might be placed. This is because these sectors are made up of 52.2% of the Jordanian listed corporations (ASE, 2017).

Furthermore, those sections also suffer from poor performance and poor level of CG and faced a drop in GDP in the last few years, as revealed by The World Bank 2020. On the other hand, this study excludes the financial sector because of its own characteristics and regulations that make it different from the other two sectors.

Table 1: depicts the number of registered corporations in ASE from 2017 to 2022.

Table 1: Sample

Service sector		Industrial sector	
Health	18	Textiles, Leathers, and Clothing	6
Educational	30	Electrical Industries	12
Hotels and Tourism	48	Engineering and Construction	36
Transportation	48	Mining and Extraction Industries	42
Technology & Communication	12	Tobacco and Cigarettes	6
Utilities and Energy	24	Food and Beverages	48
Commercial Services	48	Chemical Industries	30
		Pharmaceutical and Medical Industries	18
Total	228	Total	198

Measurement of variables

The following table elaborates measurement of independent variables, dependent variables and moderate.

Table 2: Measurement of variables

Dependent Variables		
Dependent Variables	Definition	Hypothesis
ROA	“Return on assets is measured as net income to total assets ratio (Burca & Batrîncă, 2014).”	
Tobin Q (TQ)	“Measured by adding the equity market value of the corporation and debt book value divided by the book value of a total asset (Jermias & Gani, 2014).”	
Independent Variables		
Board Size (BISZ)	“The total number of directors that serve on a corporation board, including the corporation chairman and chief executive officer (Abu Haija, 2012).”	H1 (H1 _a , H1 _b)
Board Independence (BIND)	“Measured and calculated by the proportion of independent non-executive directors to total board members (Alabdullah et al., 2014).”	H2 (H2 _a , H2 _b)
Board meeting (BIDM)	“The number of board meetings held in a year (Makhlouf et al., 2017).”	H3 (H3 _a , H3 _b)
CEO Duality (CEOD)	“If the roles of CEO and chairman are combined, the dummy variable should “e” et to “1,” and it should “e”set to “0” otherwise (Al-Matari et al., 2012).”	H4 (H4 _a , H4 _b)
Audit committee size (ACSI)	“The total number of members serving on the audit committee (Baatwah et al., 2019).”	H5 (H5 _a , H5 _b)
Audit committee meeting (ACME)	“The frequency number of meetings during a year for the audit committee (Kusnadi et al., 2016).”	H6 (H6 _a , H6 _b)
CSR (community and environment)	“Dummy variable ‘1’ if corporation has corporate social responsibility (community, environ’e’t) and ‘0’ otherwise (Pucheta et al., 2019).”	H7 (H7 _a , H7 _b)
Risk committee (RIC)	“Dummy variable where 1 the existence of RIC and 0 no RIC (Subramaniam et al., 2009).”	H8 (H8 _a , H8 _b)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Descriptive Statistics

Calculating the average, range (from minimum to maximum), and standard deviation for each variable that will be looked at in the study is the objective of the descriptive analysis. This will allow the researcher to better understand the data.

Table 3: Descriptive Statistics of Variables

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
BISZ	426	3	15	8.38	2.695
BIND	426	0	6	2.60	1.063
BIDM	426	0	15	7.34	2.080
CEOD	426	0	1	.28	.450
ACSI	426	0	6	2.98	1.016
ACME	426	0	6	3.99	1.109
CSR	426	0	1	.73	.447
RIC	426	0	1	.49	.501
ROA	426	-12.6600	19.0600	4.023238	6.4041866
TQ	426	.1100	5.4500	1.796667	1.2121317

Table 4 Autocorrelation Analysis for Model ROA and Tobin Q

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
ROA	.526a	.263	.274	5.4731654	1.778
Tobin Q	.666a	.443	.433	.9078792	1.783

The Durbin-Watson statistics are used as a tool to assess the presence of autocorrelation in the residuals of a regression study. According to (Kazmier, 1996), the Durbin-Watson statistic is considered acceptable when it falls within the range of 0 to 4. A number below 1.4 suggests a more pronounced positive correlation issue among the sample data, while a value over 2.6 mentions a more pronounced negative autocorrelation issue. Based on the data shown in Table 5.10, the Durbin-Watson parameter for the ROA Model is recorded as 1.778, whereas Tobin's Q model has a value of 1.783. Hence, the collected data does not exhibit any autocorrelation concerns.

Hypothesis Testing

The use of agency theory and resource dependency theory frameworks enables the development of four distinct models, which serve the purpose of examining and evaluating the correlation between CG and corporate financial performance. Where two models are set to explore the direct relationship and two to test the moderate variables. In this research, Model 1 examines the effect of caproate governance systems on corporate financial performance, specifically focusing on the measurement of Return on Assets (ROA). Model 2 assesses the effect of CG structures on the financial performance of corporations, specifically using Tobin's Q as the metric.

Table 5: Model of Study

Model of Study	
Model 1	"ROA = $\beta_0 + \beta_1BISZ_{it} + \beta_2BIND_{it} + \beta_3BIDM_{it} + \beta_4CEOD_{it} + \beta_5ACSI_{it} + \beta_6ACME_{it} + \beta_7CSR_{it} + \beta_8RIC_{it} + \epsilon_{it}$ "
Model 2	"TQ = $\beta_0 + \beta_1BISZ_{it} + \beta_2BIND_{it} + \beta_3BIDM_{it} + \beta_4CEOD_{it} + \beta_5SACSI_{it} + \beta_6ACME_{it} + \beta_7CSR_{it} + \beta_8RIC_{it} + \epsilon_{it}$ "

Multiple regression is a common statistical method employed by researchers such as (Haji, 2014; Ahmed Haji & Mubaraq, 2015; Paniagua et al., 2018; Kyere & Ausloos 2021; Dakhli, A. 2022).

Table 6: Hypothesis testing

	Model 1 (ROA)			Model 2 Tobin Q		
	Beta	t	Sig.	Beta	t	Sig.
(Constant)		-6.988	.000		-7.581	.000
BISZ	.085	1.548	.122	.411	8.523	.000
BIND	-.012	-.229	.819	-.111	-2.455	.015
BIDM	.137	3.097	.002	.141	3.649	.000
CEOD	.095	2.254	.025	.007	.192	.848
ACSI	.292	6.112	.000	.164	3.931	.000
ACME	.027	.558	.577	.171	4.049	.000
CSR	.175	3.888	.000	.113	2.844	.005
RIC	.111	2.519	.012	.105	2.729	.007

*Significant level at the 0.1 level **Significant level at the 0.05 level ***Significant level at the 0.01 level.

The first hypothesis makes the prediction that the size of the corporation's BODs (BSIZ) has a significant link to the corporate financial performance. Based on the findings of the regression analysis conducted on the variables of BSIZ and ROA, as shown in Table 6, it may be inferred that there is no statistically significant association between BSIZ and return on asset ($t = 1.548$, $p = .122$). The conclusion was derived from the findings of the regression analyses conducted on the variables of BSIZ and ROA. The findings of the research suggest that there is no significant correlation between the number of board members and the level of financial performance shown by corporations in Jordan. In other terms, it might be argued that the mere existence of a substantial board membership does not adequately guarantee a favourable return on assets. The findings of Tobin's Q model indicate a statistically significant link between the number of board members and Tobin's Q ($t=8.523$, $p=0.000$). As shown in Table 6, Tobin's Q of the Jordanian corporations rises when there are more directors on the board. This indicates that corporations with a higher proportion of board members have a greater propensity to substantially enhance their corporation's financial performance. The fact that there was a substantial correlation between BSIZ and Tobin's Q provides support for the notion that boards with smaller surface areas tend to have lower effectiveness (Jensen, 1993). In addition, several studies have provided empirical evidence confirming the presumption of agency theory that there is a link between a large BISZ and the financial performance of corporations (Talbi et al., 2015 and Alaryan 2017). Therefore, hypothesis H1 receives support from the Tobin's Q model.

The second hypothesis makes the prediction that there is a substantial link between the independence of the corporation's BODs (BIND) and the corporate financial performance. The insignificant link between BIND and return on asset (i.e., $t = -.229$, $p = .819$), as shown by the findings of the regression analysis done BIND and financial performance of a corporation as measured by the ROA model, which is provided in Table 6. These findings may be found by looking at the previous table. According to the findings of the investigation, there does not seem to be a significant correlation between the number of independent board members and the level of corporation financial performance that occurs in Jordan. Hence, the existence of a sizable number of Independence members is not sufficient to guarantee a strong return on investments. This result is consistent with (Orazalin et al., 2015). However, the regression results of this research utilising the Tobin Q model demonstrate that there is a substantial correlation between BIND and Tobin Q ($t = -2.455$, $P= 015$). These findings are given in Table 6. This outcome was expected, and it suggests that the controlling function of the more BIND might have a major negative effect on corporate financial performance. The potential explanation for the negative link between BIND and corporate financial performance might be attributed to the

potential neutralisation of independent directors' authority. This may occur when independent directors are appointed without necessary expertise or lack of understanding of how to effectively wield executive functions. Furthermore, according to (Wallison 2006), independent directors play a crucial role in enhancing governance rather than directly impacting the financial performance of the corporation. The prediction was because this result was identical to the one that was obtained. Therefore, Tobin's Q model lends some credence to hypothesis 2. The present research has shown that there exists a considerable link between board meetings and corporate performance, as seen by the results obtained from both the ROA and Tobin's Q models ($t = 3.097, 3.649$ and $P = .002, .000$) respectively. Hypothesis 3 predicts that the meeting of the corporation's BODs (BIDM) has a significant link to corporate financial performance. This conclusion is backed by the finding of (Alshaboul and Abu Zraiq 2020), which demonstrates that the efficacy of a board is connected to board meetings. This finding is corroborated by the research conducted by (Greco 2011). According to the findings of (Arora and Sharma 2016), productive meetings are necessary to guarantee good board performance. Furthermore, this conclusion is comparable to the findings of (Danoshana and Ravivathani 2019). The results show that corporate financial performance may be improved by raising the number of meetings it has. This result mentioned that the frequency of board meetings in Jordanian corporations is connected, in some way, to the financial performance of corporations. This research suggests that corporations that have a greater number of meetings during the financial year have superior overall performance. The third hypothesis (H3) is supported by the findings of our investigation.

The fourth hypothesis predicts that there is a substantial link between CEO and corporate financial performance. As a result, the data presented in Table 6 demonstrates that there is a statistically significant connection between CEO and ROA ($t = 2.254, P = .025$). This discovery aligns with the principles of agency theory as it confirms the distinct roles and duties of the board chairman and the CEO. Consequently, they are expected to mitigate any conflicts of interest and maintain efficient managerial oversight. This discovery illustrates the distinct requirements of the chairman of the board and the CEO, so confirming that these two positions entail divergent responsibilities. Furthermore, these results are close to the findings of (Fauver et al., 2017 and Withers and Fitza 2017). Conversely, Tobin's Q model produced statistically insignificant findings ($t = .192, p = .848$). The results are close to those of other research, such as the one conducted by (Wan and Ong, 2005), which found that there is no significant association between having a dual role as CEO and corporate financial performance. The results of the current research are close to those of earlier researchers Such as (Schmid & Zimmermann, 2008). This conclusion may be supported based on several different causes including variations in corporate legislation, capital markets, the internal capital structure of the corporation, and the structure of corporate ownership. As a result, hypothesis 4 is supported by the ROA model.

The fifth hypothesis posited that there would be a significant correlation between the size of the audit committee and corporate financial performance. The finding presented in Table 6 indicates a statistically significant association between the size of the audit committee (ACSI) and the financial performance of the corporation, as measured by the return on assets (ROA) and Tobin Q ($t = 6.112, p = 0.000, t = 3.931, p = 0.000$). This suggests that corporations with a larger value of AC members are more likely to experience significant enhancements in their financial performance as a corporation. The correlation is substantiated by the resource dependence theory, as posited by (Aldamen et al., 2012). Therefore, the efficacy of an audit committee is enhanced as the committee's size expands, as it is endowed with a greater pool of resources to effectively tackle the challenges encountered by the corporation. As a result, hypothesis 5 is supported. Based on the results of the regression analysis conducted on the relation between Audit committee meetings and return on asset (ROA), as displayed in Table 6, it can be concluded that there is no statistically significant link between Audit committee meetings and return on asset ($t = 558, p = .577$). The conclusion was derived from the findings obtained

through the regression analysis conducted on the link between the size of the Audit committee and the return on asset (ROA) model. The findings of the analysis suggest that there is no significant correlation between the number of Audit committee meetings and the level of financial performance exhibited by corporations in Jordan. In alternative terms, it can be argued that the mere existence of a substantial quantity of Audit committee meetings does not adequately guarantee a favourable return on assets. The findings of Tobin's Q model indicated a statistically significant link among of Audit committee meetings and Tobin Q ($t=4.049$, $p=0.000$). Based on the research outcomes, it has been observed that the financial performance of Jordanian corporations, as quantified by Tobin's Q, exhibits an upward trend in conjunction with an increase in the number of meetings held by the Audit committee. This suggests that corporations that hold higher number of meetings of Audit committees are more likely to significantly enhance their financial performance of the corporation. Hence hypothesis 6 is supported by Tobin Q model. The hypothesis posits that there exists a positive correlation between corporate social responsibility (CSR) and corporate financial performance. The regression analysis conducted between the variables of corporate social responsibility (CSR) and return on assets (ROA), as presented in Table 6, reveals a statistically significant positive relationship ($t = 3.888$, $P = .000$). In a similar vein, the utilisation of the Tobin Q model reveals a noteworthy and favourable correlation between Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) and Tobin Q, as demonstrated in Table 6 ($t = 2.844$, $P = .005$). The results of the current study align with prior research (e.g., Al-Smadi & Almsafir, 2016; Flammer, 2013; Abu Faraha & Alkhalaleh, 2016) which also observed a notable and statistically significant correlation between CSR and the financial performance of corporation. This suggests that the implementation of Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) practises in Jordanian corporations is associated with a positive impact on the financial performance corporations. This discovery provides evidence in favour of the proposed hypothesis. The hypothesis suggests that there is a link between risk committees and corporate financial performance. The statistical analysis performed on the link between the variables of the Risk Committee and return on assets (ROA), as presented in Table 6, demonstrates a significant association ($t = 2.519$, $P = .012$). Similarly, the application of the Tobin Q model demonstrates a significant and positive association between Risk Committee and Tobin Q, as evidenced in Table 6 ($t = 2.729$, $P = .007$). The results of the current investigation agree with those that were found in previous research conducted by (Kommunuri et al., 2016 and Tavakoli and Abu Talib, 2014). These prior studies also identified a significant and noteworthy association between the presence of a risk committee and corporate financial performance. This finding implicit that the presence of risk committee practises in Jordanian corporations is correlated with a favourable influence on the financial performance of the corporation. The finding offers substantiation for the postulated hypothesis.

CONCLUSION

According to the JCGC (2009), the recommended range for the quantity of board members falls within the spectrum of 5 to 13 (JSC, 2017). The results of the descriptive statistics shown in Table 3 indicate that some service and industrial corporations are not in adherence with the CG code. The outcome of the Return on Assets (ROA) model suggests that the direction is not statistically significant. The results and outcome presented in this study align with the results of (Makhlouf et al., 2017). On the contrary, this study has shown a substantial correlation among BISZ and Tobin Q. The finding of this research is close to the finding of (Potharla, and Amirishetty, 2021). A hypothesis on the relationship between corporation financial performance and BISZ is found to be partially supported. A board with sufficient experience and knowledge should ensure board effectiveness (AL-Matari et al., 2012). The result of this research indicates that there is a positive correlation between the size of BODs and corporate financial performance. Specifically, larger boards are shown to be more effective and efficient in enhancing the overall financial performance of the corporation. A board including members with

extensive expertise and knowledge is likely to contribute to the efficacy of the board, hence resulting in improved corporate financial performance. This outcome is indicative of a positive correlation, indicating that the variable of BISZ has a significant role in overseeing and regulating the activities of the management.

This research expected a significant relation among BIND and the financial performance of a corporation. The outcome of the Return on Assets (ROA) model showed an insignificant association between BIND and corporate financial performance. One potential rationale for this outcome could be that corporations with higher proportions of independent directors may exhibit diminished corporate financial performance. This could be attributed to the independent directors' limited familiarity with the corporation's operations, their non-full-time employment status within the corporation, and their potential challenges in comprehending the intricacies and complexities faced by the corporation. The present research provides empirical evidence that supports the agency theory by establishing a statistically significant and negative correlation between BIND and corporation performance. A negative correlation exists between an increased proportion of independent directors and a greater value of Tobin's Q. This finding provides inconsistent empirical support for the resource dependence theory posits that external directors frequently contribute valuable skills, talents, experience, and expertise to corporations. Consequently, this can't assist in effectively managing the corporations' external dependencies by facilitating the establishment of stronger corporation networks with influential stakeholders.

One possible explanation for this result might be that corporations with a greater percentage of independent directors may experience a decline in their overall financial performance. This phenomenon may be ascribed to the independent directors' restricted acquaintance with the business's activities, their part-time job position inside the corporate structure, and their possible difficulties in grasping the subtleties and complexities encountered by the corporation. Hence, hypothesis 2 is partially supported. Hence, the concept of BIND assumes a significant role in the oversight of administration, as posited by the agency theory. It is noteworthy to mention that the JCGC (2009) stipulated the inclusion of three non-executive members on the BODs. However, numerous industrial and services corporations within the ASE have failed to adhere to the provisions outlined in this Code, particularly those with smaller board sizes as a result, the board independence is 0 as shown in Table 3 in the descriptive statistics section.

According to the JCGC 2009, it is stipulated that the BODs shall convene regular meetings to effectively fulfil their duties and obligations. These meetings are intended to facilitate discussions on many significant matters about the corporation, such as the evaluation of management performance and overall corporate financial performance. The findings of the present research demonstrate a statistically significant and positive link among board meetings and the ROA model as well as Tobin's Q model. The observed correlation indicates a positive and statistically significant association between the board meetings conducted by corporations throughout the year and the overall performance of these corporations.

This conclusion is close with the research done by (Buchdadi, et al., 2019), who advocate for the agency theory. According to this theory, boards that convene on a regular and frequent basis and provide appropriate guidance, oversight, and disciplinary measures to management are likely to improve corporate financial performance. Furthermore, according to the Jordanian Corporate Governance Code (JCGC, 2009), it is recommended that the BODs in Jordan have a minimum of 4 meetings throughout a fiscal year. It was discovered that seven board meetings were the average amount held each year in Jordan, with a range of 0 to 14 meetings. This finding indicates that there is a lack of adherence to the Corporate Governance Code (2009) among some Jordanian listed corporations operating in the services and industrial sectors.

The result of this research suggests a significant connection between CEO duality and return on assets (ROA). The obtained outcome contradicts our initial predictions. The observed direction of this link aligns with previous research that has shown a positive association between the duality of positions and corporate financial performance (AlMatari et al., 2012). On the contrary, according to agency theory, it has been stated that the presence of duality inside a board structure might have a detrimental effect on its supervisory role.

Additionally, the CEO is afforded the ability to oversee opportunistic conduct due to their authoritative position over the board (Buchanan et al., 2021). Opposed to the viewpoint presented by the agency theory, the impact of CEO duality on corporate financial performance is shown to be statistically inconsequential when examined through the lens of Tobin's Q model. This indicates that there is no substantial correlation between CEO duality and corporate financial performance. Hence, the findings of this research do not assist the AT, which suggests that CEO duality reduces the surveillance role of BODs about upper-level management. This reduction in monitoring may have a negative impact on corporate performance (Buchanan et al., 2021). This conclusion is substantiated by a prior study conducted by (Makhlouf et al., (2017), which concluded that CEO duality has a negligible correlation with Tobin's Q. According to the JCGC (2009), it is explicitly prohibited for an individual to simultaneously hold the roles of chairman of the BODs and any executive position inside the corporations. Based on the findings of descriptive statistics, it has been observed that some Jordanian corporations have yet to adhere to the Jordanian Corporate Governance Code (2009).

The obtained outcome aligns with the proposed hypothesis that there exists a strong link between the size of the audit committee and the financial performance of the corporation. Consequently, the hypothesis is supported for both model ROA and Tobin Q. This finding is close to the result of (Zraiq and Fadzil 2018 and Rahman et al., 2019). As a result, the conclusions of this study are consistent with the precepts of the RDT, which posits that the effectiveness of an AC increases in tandem with its size, since a larger committee may use the diverse experience and capabilities of its members.

As mentioned in the Jordanian Code of Corporate Governance of 2009, it is stipulated that the minimum frequency of meetings should be 4 times during the fiscal year (JSC, 2017). The results of the Return on Assets (ROA) model suggest that there is no statistically significant association or effect. The results and outcomes given in this research are consistent with the results reported by (Aldamen, et al., 2012). In contrast, the findings of this study have shown a significant link between the frequency of audit committee meetings and Tobin's Q. The theory on the relationship between the financial performance of corporation and audit committee meetings is found to be somewhat substantiated. Therefore, it is important to recognise the significance of these meetings in addressing any challenges that may arise during the fiscal year, ultimately contributing to the enhancement of corporate financial performance. Based on the tenets of agency theory, it may be argued that convening audit committee meetings has the potential to positively impact corporation's financial performance. According to the Jordanian Corporate Governance Code, it is advisable for the audit committee in Jordan to have a minimum of 4 meetings throughout each fiscal year. In the context of Jordan, it was determined that the mean number of audit committee meetings was 4, exhibiting a variation between 0 and 6 meetings. This discovery suggests that several Jordanian listed corporations in the services and industrial sectors are not fully complying with the Corporate Governance Code (2009).

The findings of this research provide support for the idea that there is a link between corporate social responsibility (CSR) and corporate financial performance. The findings of the present research demonstrate a statistically significant correlation between corporate social responsibility (CSR) and the return on assets (ROA) and Tobin's Q models. This implies that a rise in the dimensions of corporate

social responsibility (CSR) would result in an augmentation of the financial performance of Jordanian corporations that are registered. The results of the current study align with other research (e.g., Al-Smadi & Almsafir, 2016) which also observed a significant correlation between corporate social responsibility (CSR) and financial performance. This suggests that the implementation of corporate social responsibility (CSR) practises in Jordanian enterprises is associated with a positive effect on their financial performance.

As stated in the Jordanian Corporate Governance Code (2009), the BODs have the authority to form additional committees as required, taking into consideration the specific characteristics of the corporation's operations. The "other committees the BODs may establish such as CG committee, risk committee, human resources committee, executive committee, product development committee". The findings of this research provide support for the idea that there is a link between risk committees and the financial performance of corporations. The results of the present research demonstrate a statistically significant link between the risk committee and the return on assets (ROA) and Tobin's Q models. This indicates that the presence of a risk committee would lead to an improvement in the financial performance of registered Jordanian corporations. In other words, if the BODs use their authority according to the Jordanian Corporate Governance Code and establish a risk committee, this will lead to enhancing the corporate financial performance. Further investigation is necessary to have a deeper understanding of the effect of governance measures on the performance of Jordanian corporations. It would be of great interest to expand the present study to encompass additional countries in the Middle East or other developing nations. This expansion would allow for a testing of the impact of corporate governance on corporate financial performance, specifically investigating whether corporate governance mechanisms contribute to the enhancement of financial performance within these markets. Hence, it is recommended that future studies direct their attention towards other factors, such as ownership concentration, to serve as moderators and enhance comprehension of the efficacy of CG and its association with corporate financial performance. A prospective study may explore additional characteristics of the BODs, such as age and experience. Furthermore, it may also examine the attributes of the audit committee, such as 'independence and financial experience'.

Reference

- 1) Abdou, H. A., Ellelly, N. N., Elamer, A. A., Hussainey, K., & Yazdifar, H. (2021). Corporate governance and earnings management nexus: Evidence from the UK and Egypt using neural networks. *International Journal of Finance & Economics*, 26(4), 6281-6311.
- 2) Abed, S., Al-Attar, A., & Suwaidan, M. (2012). Corporate governance and earnings management: Jordanian evidence. *International business research*, 5(1), 216.
- 3) Abu Haija, A. A. (2012). *The application of fair value accounting and corporate governance and their relationship to financial statements manipulation*. (Unpublished doctoral dissertation). University Utara Malaysia, Sintok, Malaysia.
- 4) Abu-Risheh, K. E., & Al-Sa'eed, M. A. (2012). The impact of good corporate governance practices on financial reporting quality: Empirical evidence from Jordanian listed companies. *Corporate Ownership & Control*, 9(4), 179-186.
- 5) Ahmed Haji, A., & Mubaraq, S. (2015). The implications of the revised code of corporate governance on firm performance: A longitudinal examination of Malaysian listed companies. *Journal of Accounting in Emerging Economies*, 5(3), 350-380.
- 6) Al Farooque, O., Buachoom, W., & Sun, L. (2020). Board, audit committee, ownership and financial performance—emerging trends from Thailand. *Pacific Accounting Review*
- 7) Alabdullah, T. T. Y., Yahya, S., & Ramayah, T. (2014). Corporate governance mechanisms and Jordanian companies' financial performance. *Asian Social Science*, 10(22), 247.

- 8) Alagha, H. S. (2016). *Corporate governance practices and firm performance of listed companies including Islamic financial institutions in the United Arab Emirates* (Doctoral dissertation, Victoria University).
- 9) Alaryan, L. A. (2017). Exploring the role of board characteristics on enhancing financial performance of Jordanian listed companies. *International Journal of Economics and Finance*, 9(7), 99-105.
- 10) Aldamen, H., Duncan, K., Kelly, S., McNamara, R., & Nagel, S. (2012). Audit committee characteristics and firm performance during the global financial crisis. *Accounting & finance*, 52(4), 971-1000.
- 11) Aldhamari, R., Nor, M. N. M., Boudiab, M., & Mas' ud, A. (2020). The impact of political connection and risk committee on corporate financial performance: evidence from financial firms in Malaysia. *Corporate Governance: The International Journal of Business in Society*.
- 12) Alharasis, E. E., & Mustafa, F. (2023). The effect of the Covid-19 epidemic on auditing quality and the reaction of family vs non-family businesses to Covid-19: the case of Jordan. *Journal of Family Business Management*.
- 13) Alix Valenti, M., Luce, R., & Mayfield, C. (2011). The effects of firm performance on corporate governance. *Management Research Review*, 34(3), 266-283.
- 14) Alkayed, H., & Omar, B. F. (2023). Determinants of the extent and quality of corporate social responsibility disclosure in the industrial and services sectors: the case of Jordan. *Journal of Financial Reporting and Accounting*, 21(5), 1206-1245.
- 15) Alkhalailah, E. A. F. M. (2016). The Relationship between Corporate Social Responsibility's Disclosure and Financial Performance: An Empirical Study of Jordanian Companies Listed on Amman Stock Exchange. *Jordan Journal of Business Administration*, 12(2).
- 16) Alkurdi, A., Hamad, A., Thneibat, H., & Elmarzouky, M. (2021). Ownership structure's effect on financial performance: An empirical analysis of Jordanian listed firms. *Cogent Business & Management*, 8(1), 1939930.
- 17) Al-Manaseer, M. F. A., Al-Hindawi, R. M., Al-Dahiyat, M. A., & Sartawi, I. I. (2012). The impact of corporate governance on the performance of Jordanian banks. *European Journal of Scientific Research*, 67(3), 349-359.
- 18) Almarayeh, Taha. "Board gender diversity, board compensation and firm performance. Evidence from Jordan." *Journal of Financial Reporting and Accounting* 21, no. 3 (2023): 673-694.
- 19) Al-Matari, Y. A., Al-Swidi, A. K., Fadzil, F. H. B. H., & Al-Matari, E. M. (2012). Board of directors, audit committee characteristics and the performance of Saudi Arabia listed companies. *International Review of Management and Marketing*, 2(4), 241-251.
- 20) Alshaboul, M. T., & Zraiq, M. A. A. (2020). Investigating the Relationship between Board of Directors and Corporate Financial in Jordan. *Journal of Finance and Accounting*, 8(2), 59-63.
- 21) Al-Smadi, A. W., & Almsafir, M. K. (2016). The Relationship between Corporate Social Responsibility and Financial Performance in Jordanian Local Banks: Panel Data Approach. *Journal of Advanced Social Research Vol*, 6(1), 01-19.
- 22) Amman Stock Exchange (ASE), 2017. Retrieved from <https://www.ase.com.jo/>
- 23) Amman Stock Exchange, 2019, 'Annual Report', Jordan, Amman Stock Exchange, online version available at <https://www.ase.com.jo/en>.
- 24) Amran, A., Zain, M. M., Sulaiman, M., Sarker, T., & Ooi, S. K. (2013). Empowering society for better corporate social responsibility (CSR): The case of Malaysia. *Kajian Malaysia*, 31(1), 57.
- 25) Arora, A., & Sharma, C. (2016). Corporate governance and firm performance in developing countries: evidence from India. *Corporate governance*, 16(2), 420-436.

- 26) Azuma, K., Dahan, N. M., & Doh, J. (2023). Shareholder reaction to corporate philanthropy after a natural disaster: an empirical exploration of the "signaling financial prospects" explanation. *Asia Pacific Journal of Management*, 1-29.
- 27) Baatwah, S. R., Salleh, Z., & Stewart, J. (2019). Audit committee chair accounting expertise and audit report timeliness: The moderating effect of chair characteristics. *Asian Review of Accounting*.
- 28) Badu, E. A., & Appiah, K. O. (2017). The impact of corporate board size on firm performance: evidence from Ghana and Nigeria. *Research in Business and Management*, 4(2), 1-12.
- 29) Baliga, B. R., Moyer, R. C., & Rao, R. S. (1996). CEO duality and firm performance: What's the fuss?. *Strategic management journal*, 17(1), 41-53.
- 30) Bowen, H. R. (1953). *Social Responsibilities of the Businessman*, Harper & Brothers. New York.
- 31) Brown, D. R., Kjaer, S. K., Sigurdsson, K., Iversen, O. E., Hernandez-Avila, M., Wheeler, C. M., ... & Barr, E. (2009). The impact of quadrivalent human papillomavirus (HPV; types 6, 11, 16, and 18) L1 virus-like particle vaccine on infection and disease due to oncogenic nonvaccine HPV types in generally HPV-naive women aged 16–26 years. *The Journal of infectious diseases*, 199(7), 926-935.
- 32) Buchanan, J. L., Commerford, B. P., & Wang, E. (2021). Auditor actions and the deterrence of manager opportunism: The importance of communication to the board and consistency with peer behavior. *The Accounting Review*, 96(3), 141-163.
- 33) Buchdadi, A. D., Ulupui, I. G. K. A., Dalimunthe, S., Pamungkas, B. G., & Fauziyah, Y. (2019). Board of director meeting and firm performance. *Academy of Accounting and Financial Studies Journal*, 23(2), 1-7.
- 34) Burca, A. M., & Batrinca, G. (2014). The determinants of financial performance in the Romanian insurance market. *International Journal of Academic Research in Accounting, Finance and Management Sciences*, 4(1), 299-308.
- 35) Carroll, A. B. (1999). Corporate social responsibility: Evolution of a definitional construct. *Business & society*, 38(3), 268-295.
- 36) Chechet, I. L., Yancy, F. S., & Akanet, S. (2013). Impact of internal governance mechanisms on corporate performance in deposit money banks in Nigeria. *International Journal of Arts and Commerce*, 2(8), 35-46.
- 37) Dakhli, A. (2022). The impact of corporate social responsibility on firm financial performance: does audit quality matter?. *Journal of Applied Accounting Research*, 23(5), 950-976.
- 38) Dalton, D. R., & Kesner, I. F. (1987). Composition and CEO duality in boards of directors: An international perspective. *Journal of International Business Studies*, 18, 33-42
- 39) Danoshana, Sooriyakumar, and Thuraisingam Ravivathani. "The impact of the corporate governance on firm performance: A study on financial institutions in Sri Lanka." *SAARJ Journal on Banking & Insurance Research* 8, no. 1 (2019): 62-67.
- 40) De Zwaan, L., Stewart, J., & Subramaniam, N. (2011). Internal audit involvement in enterprise risk management. *Managerial auditing journal*.
- 41) Elamer, A. A., & Benyazid, I. (2018). The impact of risk committee on financial performance of UK financial institutions. *International Journal of Accounting and Finance*, 8(2), 161-180.
- 42) Fama, E. F., & Jensen, M. C. (1983). Separation of ownership and control. *The journal of law and Economics*, 26(2), 301-325.
- 43) Fauver, L., Hung, M., Li, X., & Taboada, A. G. (2017). Board reforms and firm value: Worldwide evidence. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 125(1), 120-142.
- 44) Fauzi, F., & Locke, S. (2012). Board structure, ownership structure and firm performance: A study of New Zealand listed-firms.

- 45) Flammer, C. (2013). Corporate social responsibility and shareholder reaction: The environmental awareness of investors. *Academy of Management Journal*, 56(3), 758-781.
- 46) Gerged, A. M., Albitar, K., & Al-Haddad, L. (2023). Corporate environmental disclosure and earnings management—The moderating role of corporate governance structures. *International Journal of Finance & Economics*, 28(3), 2789-2810.
- 47) Ghabayen, M. A. M. (2012). *Board Characteristics and Firm Performance: Case of Saudi Arabia* (Doctoral dissertation, Universiti Utara Malaysia).
- 48) Greco, G. (2011). Determinants of board and audit committee meeting frequency: Evidence from Italian companies. *Managerial Auditing Journal*, 26(3), 208-229.
- 49) Habbash, M. (2010). *The effectiveness of corporate governance and external audit on constraining earnings management practice in the UK* (Doctoral dissertation, Durham University).
- 50) Hahn, P. D., & Lasfer, M. (2016). Impact of foreign directors on board meeting frequency. *International review of financial analysis*, 46, 295-308.
- 51) Haji, A. A. (2014). The relationship between corporate governance attributes and firm performance before and after the revised code: Some Malaysian evidence. *International Journal of Commerce and Management*, 24(2), 134-151.
- 52) Hamdan, A. M., Mushtaha, S., & Musleh Al-Sartawi, A. (2013). The audit committee characteristics and earnings quality: Evidence from Jordan. *Australasian Accounting Business and Finance Journal*, 7(4).
- 53) Hashim, U. J., & Abdul Rahman, R. (2011, November). Board independence, board diligence, board expertise and impact on audit report lag in Malaysian market. In *Finance and Corporate Governance Conference*.
- 54) Hillman, A. J., Cannella, A. A., & Paetzold, R. L. (2000). The resource dependence role of corporate directors: Strategic adaptation of board composition in response to environmental change. *Journal of Management studies*, 37(2), 235-256.
- 55) Hsu, W. Y., & Petchsakulwong, P. (2010). The impact of corporate governance on the efficiency performance of the Thai non-life insurance industry. *The Geneva Papers on Risk and Insurance-Issues and Practice*, 35(1), S28-S49.
- 56) Iskandar, T. M., Rahmat, M. M., Noor, N. M., Saleh, N. M., & Ali, M. J. (2011). Corporate governance and going concern problems: evidence from Malaysia. *International Journal of Corporate Governance*, 2(2), 119-139.
- 57) Issarawornrawanich, P. (2015). The Association between Board of Directors' Characteristics and Firm Performance: Empirical Evidence from Emerging Market of Thailand. *Journal of Applied Business & Economics*, 17(1).
- 58) Jaafar, A., & El-Shawa, M. (2009). Ownership concentration, board characteristics and performance: evidence from Jordan. In *Accounting in Emerging Economies*. Emerald Group Publishing Limited.
- 59) Jamaludin, N. D., Sanusi, Z. M., & Kamaluddin, A. (2015). Board structure and earnings management in Malaysian government linked companies. *Procedia Economics and Finance*, 28, 235-242.
- 60) Jensen, M. C. (1993). The modern industrial revolution, exit, and the failure of internal control systems. *The Journal of Finance*, 48(3), 831-880.
- 61) Jensen, M. C., & Meckling, W. H. (1976). Theory of the firm: Managerial behavior, agency costs and ownership structure. *Journal of financial economics*, 3(4), 305-360.
- 62) Jermias, J., & Gani, L. (2014). The impact of board capital and board characteristics on firm performance. *The british accounting review*, 46(2), 135-153.

- 63) Jia, J., & Bradbury, M. E. (2020). Complying with best practice risk management committee guidance and performance. *Journal of Contemporary Accounting & Economics*, 16(3), 100225.
- 64) Jordan Securities Commission (JSC). (2009). *Corporate governance code for shareholding companies listed on the Amman Stock Exchange*. Retrieved from http://sdc.com.jo/english/index.php?option=com_content&task=view&id=372
- 65) Jordan Securities Commission (JSC). (2017). Retrieved from <https://www.jsc.gov.jo/>
- 66) Karim, S., Naeem, M. A., & Ismail, R. B. (2023). Re-configuring ownership structure, board characteristics and firm value nexus in Malaysia: the role of board gender and ethnic diversity. *International Journal of Emerging Markets*, 18(12), 5727-5754.
- 67) Kazmier, L. J. (1996). *Business Statistics* (third edition). McGraw-Hill.
- 68) Khan, K., Nemati, A. R., & Iftikhar, M. (2011). Impact of corporate governance on firm performance: Evidence from the tobacco industry of Pakistan. *International Research Journal of Finance and Economics*, 61(7), 14-31.
- 69) Khasawneh, S., & Al-Zawahreh, A. (2015). Future business leaders and corporate social responsibility in Jordan: a sustainable competitive approach in the 21st century. *International Journal of Management Practice*, 8(2), 137-151.
- 70) Kitzmueller, M., & Shimshack, J. (2012). Economic perspectives on corporate social responsibility. *Journal of Economic Literature*, 50(1), 51-84.
- 71) Kommunuri, J., Narayan, A., Wheaton, M., Jandug, L., & Gonuguntla, S. (2016). Firm performance and value effects of enterprise risk management. *New Zealand journal of applied business research*, 14(2), 17-28.
- 72) Kusnadi, Y., Leong, K. S., Suwardy, T., & Wang, J. (2016). Audit committees and financial reporting quality in Singapore. *Journal of business ethics*, 139(1), 197-214.
- 73) Kyere, M., & Ausloos, M. (2021). Corporate governance and firms financial performance in the United Kingdom. *International Journal of Finance & Economics*, 26(2), 1871-1885.
- 74) Makhoulouf, M. H., Laili, N. H., Ramli, N. A., & Basah, M. Y. (2017). Board of directors' effectiveness and firm performance: Evidence from Jordan. *Research Journal of Finance and Accounting*, 8(18), 23-34.
- 75) Malik, M. (2017). Enterprise Risk Management and Firm Performance: Role of the Risk Committee.
- 76) Nava, S., Lisa, M., & Jiani, Z. (2009). Corporate Governance, Company Characteristics and Establishment of a Risk Management Committee in Australia Companies. *Managerial Auditing Journal*, 24(4), 316-339.
- 77) Nawaiseh, M. E. (2015). Do Firm Size and Financial Performance Affect Corporate Social Responsibility Disclosure: Employees' and Environmental Dimensions?. *American Journal of Applied Sciences*, 12(12), 967.
- 78) Ning, Y., Xiao, Z., & Lee, J. (2017). Shareholders and managers: Who care more about corporate diversity and employee benefits?. *Journal of Management & Governance*, 21, 93-118.
- 79) Nsour, M. F., & Al-Rjoub, S. A. (2022). Building a corporate governance index (JCGI) for an emerging market: case of Jordan. *International Journal of Disclosure and Governance*, 1-17.
- 80) Obiyo, O. C., & Lenee, L. T. (2011). Corporate governance and firm performance in Nigeria. *IJEMR*, 1(4), 1-12.
- 81) Orazalin, N., Makarov, R., & Ospanova, M. (2015). Corporate governance and firm performance in the oil and gas industry of Russia. *Journal of Business Economics and Finance*, 4(4).
- 82) Palanissamy, A. (2015). CEO duality – An explorative study. *European Scientific Journal*, ESJ, 11(10), 33-44

- 83) Paniagua, J., Rivelles, R., & Sapena, J. (2018). Corporate governance and financial performance: The role of ownership and board structure. *Journal of Business Research*, 89, 229-234.
- 84) Pfeffer, J. (1972). Interorganizational influence and managerial attitudes. *Academy of Management Journal*, 15(3), 317-330.
- 85) Potharla, S., & Amirishetty, B. (2021). Non-linear relationship of board size and board independence with firm performance—evidence from India. *Journal of Indian Business Research*, 13(4), 503-532.
- 86) Psaros, J. 2009, Australian Corporate Governance: A Review and Analysis of Key Issues, Pearson, Frenchs Forest
- 87) Pucheta-Martínez, M. C., & Gallego-Álvarez, I. (2020). Do board characteristics drive firm performance? An international perspective. *Review of Managerial Science*, 14(6), 1251-1297.
- 88) Pucheta-Martínez, M. C., Bel-Oms, I., & Olcina-Sempere, G. (2019). Commitment of independent and institutional women directors to corporate social responsibility reporting. *Business Ethics: A European Review*, 28(3), 290-304.
- 89) Rahman, M. M., Meah, M. R., & Chaudhory, N. U. (2019). The impact of audit characteristics on firm performance: an empirical study from an emerging economy. *The Journal of Asian Finance, Economics and Business*, 6(1), 59-69.
- 90) Roja, P., & Sherina, J. (2015). Role of Corporate Social Responsibility in Community. Available at SSRN 2583171.
- 91) Sahasranamam, S., Arya, B., & Sud, M. (2020). Ownership structure and corporate social responsibility in an emerging market. *Asia Pacific Journal of Management*, 37, 1165-1192.
- 92) Saibaba, M. D., & Ansari, V. A. (2011). Audit Committees and Corporate Governance: A Study of Select Companies Listed in the Indian Bourses. *IUP Journal of Accounting Research & Audit Practices*, 10(3).
- 93) Schilling, J., Opiyo, F. E., & Scheffran, J. (2012). Raiding pastoral livelihoods: motives and effects of violent conflict in north-western Kenya. *Pastoralism: Research, Policy and Practice*, 2(1), 1-16.
- 94) Schmid, M. M., & Zimmermann, H. (2008). Should chairman and CEO be separated? Leadership structure and firm performance in Switzerland. *Schmalenbach Business Review*, 60, 182-204.
- 95) Shukeri, S. N., & Islam, M. A. (2012). The determinants of audit timeliness: Evidence from Malaysia. *Journal of Applied Sciences Research*, 8(7), 3314-3322.
- 96) Subramaniam, N., McManus, L., & Zhang, J. (2009). Corporate governance, firm characteristics and risk management committee formation in Australian companies. *Managerial auditing journal*.
- 97) Swamy, K., Jayasinghe, D., & Kairamkonda, V. (2011). Audit of high gentamicin levels and hearing assessment. *Archives of Disease in Childhood*, 96(Suppl 1), A33-A34.
- 98) Talbi, D., Omri, M. A., Guesmi, K., & Ftiti, Z. (2015). The role of board characteristics in mitigating management opportunism: The case of real earnings management. *Journal of Applied Business Research (JABR)*, 31(2), 661-674.
- 99) Tavakoli, S., & Talib, N. A. (2014). A comprehensive approach to relationship between COSO ERM and firm performance in construction industry. *International Research Journal of Applied and Basic Sciences*. Vol, 8(12), 2214-2220.
- 100) Torres-Reyna, O. (2007). Panel data analysis fixed and random effects using Stata (v. 4.2). *Data & Statistical Services, Princeton University*, 112.
- 101) Vu, N. H., & Nguyen, T. (2017). Impacts of corporate governance on firm performance—Empirical studies of listed Singaporean companies.
- 102) Wallison, P. J. (2006). All the rage: will independent directors produce good corporate governance?.

- 103) Wan, D., & Ong, C. H. (2005). Board Structure, Process and Performance: evidence from public-listed companies in Singapore. *Corporate Governance: An International Review*, 13(2), 277-290.
- 104) Withers, M. C., & Fitzg, M. A. (2017). Do board chairs matter? The influence of board chairs on firm performance. *Strategic Management Journal*, 38(6), 1343-1355.
- 105) World Bank. (2020). *Global economic prospects, June 2020*. The World Bank.
- 106) Yunus, R. M. (2011). *The effect of ownership concentration, board of directors, audit committee and ethnicity on conservative accounting: Malaysian evidence*. Edith Cowan University.
- 107) Zraiq, M. A. A., & Fadzil, F. H. B. (2018). The impact of ownership structure on firm performance: Evidence from Jordan. *International Journal of Accounting, Finance and Risk Management*, 3(1), 1-4.